

HBIM FOR THE “DIGITAL TWIN” MODEL SET UP OF THE CHURCH OF “NOSSA SENHORA DA PENA” IN LISBON

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ABSTRACT

This study presents applied BIM solutions to scan-to-BIM model of the church of “Nossa Senhora da Pena” in Lisbon since it is included as case of study of the interdisciplinary research project Quad2BIM, a European Commission funded project.

The church of Nossa Senhora da Pena is an important example of Portuguese historical built heritage. Despite being an important example of baroque architecture of the 18th century with clear influence of Italian art, the building remained largely under-studied until now. The church was built in 1705 and today it still preserves the wooden boarded ceiling covered with illusionist paintings and its reach golden interior.

The project assesses the application of the Heritage-Building Information Modelling (H-BIM) paradigm for the documentation and conservation management of built heritage.

We propose a different modelling development, based on the scan-to-BIM workflow, to help surveyors and BIM technicians for a collaborative approach in order to issue as-built parametric models efficiently integrate into the conservation and development design of the historic architecture and its life cycle.

Key words: HBIM, Baroque architecture, Illusionistic ceiling painting

CHURCH OF NOSSA SENHORA DA PENA, SHORT CHRONOLOGY OF ITS CONSTRUCTION

The two conditions that most likely brought, at the beginning of 18th Century, to the construction of a new church in “Calçada de Santana” were the large increase of the population, which led to the need of founding new parishes in the city, and the arrival of D. Catarina¹ to the hill of Santana.

¹ Catherine of Braganza (Portuguese: Catarina de Bragança; 25 November 1638 – 31 December 1705) was Queen of England, Scotland and Ireland from 1662 to 1685, as the wife of King Charles II. Catherine served as regent of Portugal during the absence of her brother in 1701 and during 1704–1705, after her return to her homeland as a widow.

The new population scenario, related with the overseas expansion of Portugal and its economic growth was responsible for the creation of twelve new parishes, including the Santa Ana one in 1703².

The commingling of works connected with the intent of D. Catarina, Serenissima Senhora Raynha da Gram Bretanha” to improve and dignify the connecting path from the “Collegio de Santo Antão-o-Novo” (today’s San José hospital), which belonged to the “Companhia de Jesus”, to Santa Ana, facilitated the authorization process to the “Irmandade do Santíssimo Sacramento” for the construction of the church.

The church of Nossa Senhora da Pena, which was originally called church of Sant’Ana and located into the former Sant’Ana Convent of the Third Order of San Francisco, was moved to the new site in “Calçada de Santana” and founded on March the 25th of 1705 according to Friar Agostinho de Santa Maria in “Santuário Mariano”³.

In the following decades, from 1714 to 1722, the church, which was not still entirely completed, was involved in a cycle of works for the realization of the internal decorations⁴.

On November the 1st of 1755, the church was badly shaken by the great Lisbon earthquake.

The church suffered a lot of damage by the 1755 earthquake, mainly on the facade and its main body, which left it without a roof. However, because it was not involved in the fire after the earthquake (as documented by the map in the image above), its primitive appearance was maintained through the reconstruction.

The reconstruction process took place quite fast and, in 1763, the church reopened although with certain works to be completed; it lacked a tower, the plaster of the facade and the interior decorations.

The building has a sober facade facing the east with a medallion on the top of the portal representing Nossa Senhora da Pena surrounded by angels.

The interior has a single nave without a transept, with three altars on each side and two chapels. The nave is covered by a vaulted ceiling, painted with a monumental “quadratura” composition representing architectural elements on two floors. In the middle of the 19th century and in the beginning of the 20th century the church benefited from repairs and additions. It was also desecrated in 1910 following the proclamation of the republic, reopening to worship in 1926.

The church is included in the special area of protection of properties classified as “imóveis da Avenida da Liberdade e área envolvente”⁵.

² Cfr. Mapa de Lisboa, realizado por João Nunes Tinoco em 1650, GEO. On the side.

³ Tome VII, p. 147.

⁴ Ferreira, 2009, vol. II, pp. 493, 502 and 513

⁵ Source: <http://www.monumentos.gov.pt/Site/APP_PagesUser/SIPA.aspx?id=6530> [Acesso em 23 Maio 2021].

Fig. 1: “Carta do terramoto de 1755 na parte central the Lisboa”. The church of Pena is included in the area with the highest grade of heartquake intensity but outside the limit line that describe the extension of the fire that partiali destroie the “Baixa”.

THE “QUADRATURA” PAINTING ON THE CEILING OF THE NAVE

The painting of the ceiling of the nave of Igreja da Pena, by Antonio Lobo, is one of the first examples of quadratura in Lisbon dating back to 1718 when there were not many examples of this pictorial genre in Portugal.

Antonio Lobo is considered one of the best disciples of the Italian quadraturist Bacherelli⁶, and when commissioned by the “Irmandade do Santíssimo Sacramento”, he proposed a very scenographic project. The perspective composition has a single central vanishing point and simulates false architectural effects to a viewer positioned in the canter of the nave. The painting’s support is constituted by a wooden ceiling in the shape of a cloister vault. Due to the geometry of the ceiling, made by the perpendicular intersection of two barrel vaults, the application of the drawing in perspective, the “bozzetto”, to the painting support presents some difficulties, especially in the corners because in those areas it is

⁶ Cirilo Volkmar Machado, “Colecção de Memórias (...)”, Coimbra, 1922, p.145.

Fig. 2: 3D textured mesh model of the vaulted ceiling painted by Antonio Lobo (1718) and Luiz Batista (1781).

most likely to vanish the illusionistic effect of the virtual architecture due to the change of geometry of the surfaces of the support.

The architectural representation is made up of three levels. The first one is composed of corbels that run across the lowest area of the ceiling and support the upper floor, which is hidden by the real crown molding.

The next level has a long balustrade that runs across the entire ceiling. The corners of the vault, as we just said, are the part where it is more difficult to apply perspective so, the quadraturists solved these angles with balconies that project outwards, constituting a semicircular base element that gives support to the columns of the upper level. In the space of the balustrade, both in the longitudinal and in the transversal sides, the presence of “putti” and richly decorated flower vases is frequent. The Four Evangelists are positioned in the concave recesses of the balustrade, supported by corbels. High columns with composite capitals, positioned symmetrically on both sides project the architecture upwards. They support the central arches adorned with flowerpots.

The last part of the perspective composition consists of a frame that surrounds the entire central scene and prepares the viewer’s eye for the main panel: “The coronation of the Virgin.

The central piece has a regular composition with the Holy Mary in the center. The Virgin is shown standing on the clouds surrounded by putti. The central piece does not follow the perspective plain used to construct the architectural composition of the quadrature’s sides but it share the same perspective vanishing point. The Coronation of the Blessed Virgin Mary is perpendicular to the viewer; it looks like the characters are floating horizontally rather than to be raising above the detailed architectural elements.

In this point the painting loses the illusionist depth built by the balustrades, columns and details situated at the sides of the composition.

Fig. 3: Pointcloud orthoimages and orthophoto of the painted ceiling.

SITE SURVEY, DATA PROCESSING AND HBIM PROJECT SET UP

The complex of the church of Nossa Senhora da Pena has been chosen as one of the case study of the European research project Quad2BIM⁷.

QUAD2BIM's mission is to promote Smart Heritage turning BIM (Building information modelling) in a functional instrument of knowledge, design and management for historical architecture. It aims to define an efficient working protocol for building surveyors and BIM technicians, or rather a collaborative approach for issuing as-built parametric models integrate into the development process of the existing and historic buildings.

⁷ This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 895320, MSCA-IF-2019 - Individual Fellowships website: www.quad2bim.com and Cordis web page <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/895320>

Fig. 4: Pointcloud of the church of “Nossa Senhora da Pena”.

So far, the companies that use to carry out the 3D Measured Building Survey also extract the so-called H-BIM (Heritage-BIM) 3Ds as that extremely needs a point cloud based approach and competences. Unluckily, the results often do not consider the subsequent steps of the building re-design, restoration or reconstruction cycle, which involves architects, engineers and contractors. The “information sharing”, which is the pillar of BIM methodology for new construction, in this case is inadequate and must be improved.

Applying BIM to the chosen cases of study, mainly example of Portuguese Baroque architecture, we want to face these issues, develop, and test scan-to-BIM workflows at different level of detail and development.

For the Church of Nossa Senhora da Pena, due the complexity of the architectural style, we had to integrate digital and traditional techniques to fully model the building in BIM environment.

During the survey phase, we had the chance to easily access all the interiors of the site and thank to that we decided to use only laser Scanners, Cameras and GPS for the digital data gathering; also, we found useful to use direct measurement tools and sketches made by our operators as support for modeling small elements like frames and bases profiles.

Fig. 5: “Plan A”.

To get more information and details about the painting of the vault we decide to use coloured scans for the interior of the church and a sufficient number of pictures in order to create a textured mesh model of its surface using the Structure from Motion process.

The registered point cloud eventually was made by 352 scans and the registration error was lower than 10mm, which fitted our quality and validity parameters.

The GPS survey have georeferenced the point cloud. Thanks to that, we were able to choose a Project Base Point (PBP)⁸ for setting the BIM file in the geographic coordinate system.

The PBP, when we start a Revit model, specify the location of the site and establishes a reference for measuring distances and positioning components within the context of the model⁹.

By sharing coordinates, we were being able to import the point cloud in the BIM environment and any other linked file.

The usage of georeferenced PBP is essential in any BIM projects because it allows the interoperability and the collaboration between the stakeholders through sharing the information into the same project federated-model. The PBP position must be chosen with the client. The survey company can suggest the position of that point but it always needs to be verified and formally approved by the client.

It is not convenient to start the modeling phase before setting the PBP because moving the model or the PBP can create ambiguity in the BIM project and some categories of families can become unstable because their parameters are related to the spatial position of the families.

⁸ Project Base Point definition by Autodesk <https://knowledge.autodesk.com>

⁹ ISO19650 in all its parts.

THE HBIM PROJECT LAYOUT

It is important to understand that surveyors and BIM technicians, as first operators in the HBIM project cycle are highly responsible for the quality of the model and its grade of manipulation.

As they are in charge of the setup of the HBIM project, they have to follow the main principle and rules for BIM¹⁰, which, at the operative level, it means: clearly sharing data and information according to the client need, avoiding ambiguity and rework, applying consistency to the all areas of the project.

To guarantee our team to work without hesitation and errors in the complex scan-to-BIM process, we defined the Scope of Work (SOW), or rather the model specifications, before starting the site activities in order to know the level of detail to use for both, the point cloud density and the final output, the model.

Starting from an evaluation and classification of the historic value of the areas within the building and of its surroundings, we have decided to develop a BIM project by three homogenous areas; each of them is characterized by an adequate and appropriate level of detail and accuracy according to their historic value and relevance within the project extension.

Despite the reconstruction works and the additions during the 19th and 20th Century the aspect of the main body of the church was not affected so, the richest and most complex area, in terms of details, remained its nave and the chancel, highlighted in pink (area “A”) in the “Plan A” shown above. The roof of the entire block is in area “A” too. We have excluded from area “A” the church basement (area “B”, in yellow in “Plan A”) because it has a secondary function and does not have any relevant decorations. Area “C” includes the surrounding buildings only.

The corresponding Level of Detail¹¹ (LOD) for area A is fixed at 300; the LOD for area B was “200” and for area “C” was 100.

Building detail have be manually extracted from the site measurements to create new families with the appropriate geometry in accordance with ISO 19650.

Areas “A” and “B” were needed to document both internal and external of the building. The model was commensurate with a scale of presentation of 1:50, which means the modeled features, against to the survey data, were set within 20mm deviation.

Area “C” did not include the internals as it was used only to show the volumes of the surrounding buildings. It did not contemplate any details in facade, neither doors nor windows. The model was at an accuracy commensurate with a scale of presentation of 1:100, which means its features, against to the survey data, were set within 50mm deviation.

¹⁰ © “BIM Forum” specifications for Level of Detail

INTRODUCTION TO THE MODELING APPROACH FOR THE PROPOSED CASE OF STUDY

In the case of Existing-BIM or Heritage/Historic-BIM sometimes the BIM technicians, if not supported by a team of specialists that can extract extra information beyond the metric and morphologic one, cannot easily get and share, for instance, the wall internal layering, the internal construction details, parameters related to the mechanical and thermic resistance of the material, etc. As we have been under these circumstances for the “Pena” site, we have decided to privilege the modeling aspect, while still guaranteeing the interoperability with all the stakeholders that in the future may use our model and probably will need to complete it with the information mentioned previously.

We are conscious that the implementation of models in BIM has two main aspects to be taken into account, the “Information” and the “Modeling” ones and it is also true that clients, mainly architects and engineers, often explicitly request “as-built BIM models” that do not describe the material. That usually depends on consideration of the costs of the project or it simply happens because at that stage, this information is not required. The building manager/owner anyway will get a BIM model of his/her real estate that can be integrated with the needed attribute at any phases of the building life cycle.

To make possible the application of those changes, it is necessary to use the BIM components with some consideration. In this sense, we would provide some suggestions that should affect positively the HBIM project.

PENA PROJECT MODELLING DEVELOPMENT

Regarding the modelling development, we considered the fact that in the future, architects and engineers and other professionals probably will use our model for the building “ReUse” and they will inherit the survey model and use it as basis for the re-design development. This will usually involve post strip-out survey of some areas, updates to column size, linings being redone, wall thickness changing and doors/windows replaced, etc.

Modifying an object already present in a BIM model can generate unintentional changes to the entire area in which it is placed since its parameters and qualities are related to its host family¹¹ and to the components closely connected. The way that components are modelled has huge bearing on how easy they will be to amend and update later on and, consequently, a great impact on the project time and cost consuming.

In our project, to face this issue, we used doors and windows in a different way from the default mode proposed by the software, in this case Autodesk Revit 2020. We manipulated the original families removing the “cut opening” associated to their dimensions. This way, the doors/windows, once placed on the

¹¹ BIM objects are called “families”

Fig. 6: Solution for door and windows openings.

host family, the wall, do not create the cut on it, appearing immerse into the wall. Consequently, the wall should be cut or modified in its profile to show the door/window. With this practical expedient, we marked the position of the aperture in the wall and unlinked it from the presence of door family. This workflow allows the modelling process to follow the real construction features.

In case of strip-out, it is possible to delete the existing door and keep the door aperture.

The changes proposed can be applied only on version of Revit 2020 or superior.

Another practical solution regards the walls insertion into the model and involves the the position side of its “finishing face”.

As we did not have information about the inner layering of the wall and we used generic walls for the model, we risked often to place the wall “inside out” because we did not have a timely visual control of which could be the internal or external face of it. The risk of delivering a model with walls set in the wrong direction can cause complications to whom will insert the material at a later date.

This issue usually does not happen when we model with detailed wall and can see, on external side of the it, the plaster thicker than on the internal one and use this element as reference.

The command “flip” allows swapping the wall sides on the floor plan view “mirroring” the element by the selected internal/external face, which means that this operation moves the wall from its correct position.

To avoid rework and errors on walls, we should set the insertion side on the central axis l, which means to set up, in the wall properties panel, the “Finish face” field on the “core central line” option. This way, if necessary, will be possible to “flip” the sides of the wall without moving it.

Doors/windows and walls are probably the families most used in modelling. The choices described above, if applied, affect positively the quality of the model.

At any rate, the families are not compromised in their parametric characteristics after the modification proposed. All the information related could still be analysed, tested, and included in the project Schedules tabs.

For some architectural elements that in the complex on the church we evalu-

Fig. 7: Wall solution before and after applying the insertion side on the central axis of the wall, which it means to set up, in the wall properties panel, the “Finish face” field on the “core central line” option.

ate they visibly needed to be demolished and be redone because of their precarious conservation condition – for example portion of the wooden pavement at the choir level or portion of plaster on some walls – we modeled the damaged layer as a separate component to facilitate the demolition/replacement project into the model.

In addition, we had arranged a “sheet” family in order to integrate into the BIM file the historic information on the construction phases of the building. Professional can integrate that information during the next restoration and design projects.

Fig. 8: Nossa Senhora da Pena HBIM model: walls modelling in progress. Walls have been the first elements modeled in BIM. No sweep nor other element have been applied on them before the Quality Assurance check that confirmed their correct faces orientation.

CONCLUSIONS

Nowadays, the opportunities that BIM could offer us are still undervalued since BIM is at a first stage of development and, in some cases, it is considered by the professionals hard to be adopted as “business as usual”.

The software available so far, still have some limitation for a flexible modeling.

During our experience, as for the majority of the BIM architects and technicians that are experiencing modelling into BIM environment, we had to face some critical moments due to the complexity of the interiors of the building which made slow down the modelling process and for searching ways to make our components “interoperable”.

Nevertheless, we are convinced that BIM is convenient process for managing architecture.

The convenience of a 3D database, the BIM model, that include the building elements, hold by the building manager or owner, significantly reduces the costs for the property management during the building lifecycle. BIM makes management efficiency improved since a parametric model allows testing and simulation of design costs and solutions.

Our intent is to offer new options for increasing the level of interoperability with the other project stakeholders and make more convenient the adoption of BIM also for the documentation, representation maintenance and Reuse of built Heritage, and, as they are in line with the BIM standards, they make the communication of data and information more transparent and universally recognized and validated.